

LEGALIZATION OF ABORTION: IT'S IMPLICATION ON THE NIGERIAN POPULACE

By

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Abstract

This paper examines the issue of legalization of abortion and it's implication on the Nigerian populace. It identified the factors that are responsible for procurement of induced abortion. It examined the abortion bill proposed by the National Assembly in 1981. It also examines the health hazards/related to abortion and reasons adduced for and against the legalization of abortion in the Nigerian society. It recommends among other things that abortion should be discouraged and can only be applicable if authenticated that the life of the mother and the foetus is being endangered.

INTRODUCTION

Legalization of abortion had been and is still a seriously debated issue globally. But the major concern of any society should be that of regulating sexual behaviour of individual so that they conform to the generally accepted standard or norms (McCary, 1978). However, the Nigerian society is becoming diffuse, it is becoming increasingly difficult to determine the accepted sexual attitude and behavior, (Adeniyi, 1998). Nevertheless, every society at any given point in time tends to formulate its own sexual codes and exerts control

abnormal (Adeniyi, 2006)

According to (Insel and Roth, 1982) abortion is the premature expulsion or removal of an embryo or foetus from the uterus. (Jones, Sheinberg and Byer, 1972) opined that abortion is the removal of a growing embryo or foetus from the uterus to which it is attached. (McConnell 1984) simply puts it that when conceptus which is a product of conception is expelled from the uterus permanently, then it is an abortion. However, certain authorities seem to complicate issue by defining abortion as termination, expulsion or detachment of foetus or fertilized ovum before its time of viability. (Golden, 1982). On the basis of the landmark U.S Supreme Court Case Roe VS Wade of 1973, the United State joined many of the world most populated countries in legalizing abortion with the following guidelines:

For the first three month of pregnancy (first trimester) the decision to abort lies with the woman and her doctor.

For the later weeks of pregnancy (second trimester) state laws may regulate the abortion procedure on ways that are reasonable related to maternal health.

For the last three month of pregnancy (third trimester) when the foetus is judged capable of surviving if born, any state may regulate or even prohibit abortion except where abortion is necessary to preserve the life or health of the mother. If a pregnancy is terminated during the third trimester, viable fetus would be considered a live birth and would not be allowed to die. (Gary, 1997) (Hahn and Payne,1998). In general a foetus is not viable, until the 28th week. Any mishap after the 28th week usually considered as a premature delivery.

Abortion is either spontaneous or induced. It is spontaneous abortion when is natural abortion, which is also called miscarriage. It occurs naturally, unintended and out of its own violation, and hence it is the natural termination of pregnancy by the body, (Adeniyi, 1997). While induced abortion is the intentional termination of a pregnancy before the fetus can live independently. An abortion may be elective (based on a woman's personal choice) or therapeutic (to preserve the health or save the life of a pregnant woman). (Finer & Henshaw, 2003)

(Trupin, 2003) stated that an abortion is considered to be elective if a woman chooses to end her pregnancy, and it is not for maternal or fetal health reasons. Some reasons for which a woman might choose to have an elective abortion are:

- Continuation of the pregnancy may cause emotional or financial hardship.
- The woman is not ready to become a parent.
- The pregnancy was unintended.
- The woman is pressured into having one by her partner, parents, or others.

- The pregnancy was the result of rape or incest.

A therapeutic abortion is performed in order to preserve the health or save the life of a pregnant woman. A health care provider might recommend a therapeutic abortion if the fetus is diagnosed with significant abnormalities, not expected to live and if it has died *in utero*. Therapeutic abortion may also be used to reduce the number of fetuses if a woman is pregnant with multiples; this procedure is called multifetal pregnancy reduction (MFPR).

A therapeutic abortion may be indicated if a woman has a pregnancy-related health condition that endangers her life. Some examples of such conditions include:

- severe hypertension (high blood pressure)
- cardiac disease
- severe depression or other psychiatric conditions
- serious kidney or liver disease
- certain types of infection
- malignancy (cancer)
- multifetal pregnancy

This paper focuses on induced abortion because it is the abortion that is subjected to legislation. Induced abortion has become a serious issue in Nigeria and its associated complications has in no little ways affects the lives, prospect and careers of a large numbers of young ladies in the society. The writer is of the opinion the issue of legalization of abortion should be critically analyzed and its effect on the Nigerian populace discussed. (Adeniyi, 1999), (Payne and Hahn, 1998) opined that the factors responsible for induced abortion can be classified in predisposing and enabling factors.

Predisposing factors are conditions within the society that creates psychology readiness for encouraging illegality. In present time, there are growing moral decadence and sexual laxity. The Nigerian society is not only faced with indiscriminate sexual behaviours such as pre-marital sex, extra-marital sex, exhibitionism or indecent exposure, prostitution, pornography e.t.c but also with its attendant problems like abortion in order to terminate unwanted pregnancy.

While enabling factor is the perception of adult sexual behavior by youth. The adult in the society serve as resource that the young one emulates in terms of sexual behaviours that lead to unwanted pregnancy and abortion. Adegbite (1983) stated that Nigerian society no longer regards pre-marital and extra-marital sex as a failure of moral rectitude but rather as an act of civilization. He further stated that immoral practices among ladies and woman

in the society are esteemed as sophistication.

PROBLEMS RELATED TO ABORTION

(Insel and Roth, 1982) contend that induced abortion, even when performed under ideal condition may result in a number of health problems or complication which includes the following:

- a. Incomplete abortion; which may become septic and will further require of repeat of Dilation and Curettage
- b. Infection: repeat Dilation and Curettage is prone to perforation of the uterus, hemorrhage and infections such as aids from unsterilized medical instruments.
- c. Infertility: induced abortion could result in the permanent damage of the uterus; such situation may lead to barrenes.
- d. Spontaneous abortion: this abortion may often follow planned pregnancies ending in spontaneous abortion.
- e. Premature delivery and abnormalities: premature delivery and low birth weight babies are associated with induced abortion. This may also increase the chances of abnormalities in children.
- f. Maternal mortality: a significant numbers of death occur from abortion every year. The Society for Gynecologists and Obstetricians estimated that about 20,000 Nigerian women die from unsafe abortion each year.(Federal Ministry of Health, 2002)
- g. Post partum blue: this is the type of emotional problem associated with abortion. This is characterized by feeling of guilt and depression.

ABORTION ISSUES IN NIGERIA

In Nigeria, abortion is illegal and carries a stiff jail sentence, up to 14 years, unless done to save the life of the pregnant woman. Abortion is governed by the Criminal Code in the southern states, and the Penal Code in the northern states

Nigerian law makes it a crime to perform or to obtain an abortion except to save a woman's life. Penalties exist for any person who performs an abortion, as well as for any woman who seeks an abortion or who attempts to cause her own miscarriage. Okagbue (1990)

The National Assembly then sitting in Lagos proposed an “**ABORTION BILL**” in 1981. The aims of the bill were stated to include:

- a. The prevention of the practice of abortion in back street by ill- equipped

medical doctor or quacks.

- b. To save the lives, of our young teenagers and woman which result from abortion.
- c. To stop the ruining of lives, the prospect of thousand of young women of ever rearing children due to illegal abortion.
- d. To prevent unwanted pregnancies.

This is one of the attempts to make induced abortion lawful and remove the secrecy attached to it but this attempt failed.

Other reasons adjudged for the call for legalization of abortion in Nigerian is that abortion is illegal and carries a heavy jail sentence up to 14 years imprisonment unless it is preformed to save the life of pregnant woman. Yet an estimated one million abortion are carried out in Nigeria each year. Illegal abortion is responsible for 50% of maternal deaths, particularly in adolescents and young woman. Tradition and culture tend to force young woman to seek abortion, as there are strong social sanctions against unmarried woman with children and an unmarried pregnant woman without a suitor could be ostracized. There is very little support in the country for making abortion legal on request. (Arthur, 1999)

PRO ABORTION VIEWS

Besides the tremendous benefit to society of ensuring that every child is a wanted child, legal abortion has clearly been a significant factor in saving woman's lives and health: the Childbirth by Choice Organization opined that:

- A large majority of legal abortion replace abortion that had been performed illegally, and often unsafe before, the change in laws
- Deaths from abortion have declined dramatically in all countries where abortion has been legalized
- Legal abortion is nearly twice as safe as a penicillin injection.
- Where abortion is legal and readily available, woman obtains abortions earlier in pregnancy when health risks to them are lowest.
- One third of all legal abortions are on woman for whom the health social consequences of unplanned childbearing are the greatest, teenagers and woman over 35.
- Legal abortion protects woman suffering from serious or life- threatening illnesses and genetic disease that could be passed onto their children with divesting consequences.
- When woman can control their reproduction, it leaves them free to pursue higher education and careers, and to plan their personal and economic freedom to have babies they don't want. Until that day when women, and only women, shall determine while

males must, by law have vasectomies, then and only then --- will you or any man have the right to determine which woman can have abortion.

ANTIABORTION VIEW

Despite the obvious health and social benefits. Legal abortion continues to be the victim of profound, sometimes violent, controversy. The controversy is fueled by religious dogma particularly that of the Catholic Church and fundamentalist religions, which claim that all life is sacred, and human life starts at conception. Even beyond religion doctrine, the social message is that choosing to continue a pregnancy is good: terminating it is bad, regardless of the circumstances.

This attitude has a deep effect on woman having abortions. Some women feel embarrassed, guilty, and ashamed for deciding to have an abortion. In fact, women who come to abortion clinics are often surprised when they receive professional, compassionate medical care. (Appiah, 1996).

This poisonous attitude abort abortion also has a strong effect on those providing abortion services. In some part of the world, physicians and medical staff fell stigmatized by their colleagues and society. Being an abortion provider does not carry social approval, prestige, or financial reward, compared with other specialties. Many medical schools and department of obstetrics and gynecology don't even require student to learn abortion techniques, and courses work in that field often does not even mention abortion. And remember, abortion is probably the most common surgical procedure in the world. Adeniyi (2005).

The Catholic Association of Nigerian Youth Wing State: "the inalienable rights of the person must be recognized and respected by civil society and political authorities, and such fundamental rights include the right to life from the moment of conception until death, Pope Paul VI state that from the moment of conception, the very human being is to be respected in an absolute way --- no one can, in any circumstance, claim for himself the right to destroy directly an innocent human being.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were drawn that despite the adjudged benefits of legalized abortion it is evident from the above discussion that abortion should be condemned in it entity and should not be considered for legalization. Abortion which is the premature killing of a living fetus and its attendant complications should not be encouraged by the society. The foetus which was not allowed to live would have had its own contribution to the family and the society at large. Abortion and its attendant complications have serious

implications on the family and the society. However, abortion under close supervision by medical expert can be allowed if it is for therapeutic purpose and is aimed at saving the life of the pregnant woman.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the above discussion, this writer recommends the following:
Induced abortion for therapeutic purposes by competent physicians as stipulated by law of the land should be retained for the protection of unborn child and the reduction of maternal mortality

There should be proper education on the family planning methods for limiting family size, preventing unwanted pregnancies and for population control without resulting in the use of abortion.

There should be proper education on problem associated with abortion or health implications of abortion such as infertility and high maternal mortality.

Sex education should be introduced at all levels of education so as to guide against unwholesome sexual behaviour that are prone to pregnancies that encourage induced abortion.

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